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Photochemical Reduction of Ferric Oxalate in a Solid pressed Potassium Bromide Disk

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IN continuation of our work on the photochemical reaction in solid pressed potassium bromide disk^{1,2}, we have studied the photochemical reaction of ferric oxalate.

Experimental

The transparent potassium bromide disks were prepared by mixing ferric oxalate (1 mg) with KBr (1 g) in a vibrator and the mixture was pressed under vacuum into disk (250 mg; 14.5 mm dia × 1.0 mm). The disk was irradiated with ultraviolet light from a Phillips 125 W uv lamp for 1 and 2 h and infrared spectra were recorded after each irradiation on a Perkin-Elmer 377 grating spectrophotometer, to follow the course of photochemical reactions.

Results and Discussion

The reaction products were identified by characterising the ir spectra of ferric oxalate before and after the irradiation and by chemical means. The results were also compared with the ir spectra of the disk acting as control by keeping the disk in dark and taking their spectra after 0, 1 and 2 h. No change in the position of the bands were observed, which indicates that no reaction has taken place in the dark.

The comparison of spectra before and after irradiation revealed shift of the position of several bands, and some of the bands disappeared and some new bands appeared. Gradual appearance of a

band at 2 350–2 330 cm⁻¹ was assigned to the formation of carbon dioxide³. It is observed that a broad band centered at 1 670 cm⁻¹ shifted to 1 635 cm⁻¹ (C=O)⁴. A broad band at 1 430 cm⁻¹ gradually disappeared and lost after 2 h of irradiation. The bands at 1 345 and 1 270 cm⁻¹ shifting to 1 360 and 1 315 cm⁻¹ were attributed to the $\nu_{\sigma-O} + \nu_{\sigma-\sigma}$ and $\nu_{\sigma-O} + \delta_{O-\sigma-O}$, respectively. The intensity of the band at 870 cm⁻¹ increased after irradiation which was assigned to $\nu_{\sigma-O} + \delta_{O-C-O}$ band. In the same way, the band at 805 cm⁻¹ shifting to 820 cm⁻¹ was attributed to $\delta_{O-\sigma-O} + \delta_{M-O}$. A new band appeared after irradiation at 665 cm⁻¹, and shifting of the band at 490 from 530 cm⁻¹ with the increase in band intensity was attributed to $\nu_{M-O} + \nu_{O-\sigma}$.

Thus the appearance, disappearance and shifts in the position of bands revealed the reduction of ferric oxalate into ferrous oxalate with the formation of carbon dioxide. The formation of ferrous oxalate is further confirmed by dissolving the ferric oxalate pellet before and after irradiation in the dilute solution of potassium permanganate. The permanganate solution containing irradiated pellet decolourised slowly compared to the solution containing non-irradiated pellet, inferring that ferric oxalate is reduced to ferrous oxalate according to the following stoichiometric relationship,

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Kinetics of Oxidation of Thiocyanate Ion by Dichloramine-B in Partially Aqueous Medium

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THE chemistry of *N*-halogeno-*N*-metalloaromatic sulphonamides is of interest due to their diverse behaviour. They are sources of halonium cations and hypohalite species¹. Dichloramine-B (DCB) in an important member of the benzene analogue

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NOTES

of this class of oxidants. Although the oxidation potential of it has been exploited as an analytical reagent for determining a variety of substrates in solution², there are no reports on the mechanistic investigations with DCB. As a part of our mechanistic studies with positive halogens^{3,4}, we report herein the kinetics of oxidation of thiocyanate ion by dichloramine-B (*N,N*-dichlorobenzene-sulphonamide) in 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol medium.

The oxidants so far employed for the oxidation of thiocyanate ion include H₂O₂⁵, aqueous iodine⁶, Cr^{VI} and V^V⁷, Bi^{III}⁸ and monohaloamines⁹.

Experimental

Dichloramine-B (DCB) was prepared by the chlorination of chloramine-B⁹ in aqueous solutions. The purity of the oxidant was checked by iodometric estimation of the active halogen present in it. It was further characterised by recording its ir and nmr spectra. A stock solution of the compound (~0.05 mol dm⁻³) in methanol was prepared, standardised by the iodometric method and preserved in dark coloured bottles. Potassium thiocyanate (A.R.) was dried at 423 K and its aqueous solution (~0.5 mol dm⁻³) was standardised by the argentometric method. All other chemicals employed were of accepted grades of purity. Ionic strength of the medium was maintained at 0.30 mol dm⁻³ using concentrated solution of sodium perchlorate (E. Merck).

Kinetic measurements: The kinetic studies were made in glass stoppered pyrex boiling tubes in 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol under pseudo-first order conditions, with [NCS⁻] >> [DCB] (10–200 times). The reaction was initiated by the rapid addition

of a measured quantity of DCB solution, thermally equilibrated at a desired temperature, to a mixture containing requisite amounts of thiocyanate solution, HClO₄, methanol, sodium perchlorate and water, equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reaction was monitored for two half-lives by iodometric determination of unreacted DCB at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-first order rate constants computed by the method of least-squares were reproducible within ± 3%.

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometry of DCB-NCS⁻ reaction was determined by allowing reaction mixtures containing NCS⁻ and DCB in different concentration ratios to completion at different solvent compositions and [H⁺] (0.005 to 0.20 mol dm⁻³). The sulphate and cyanate ions in the reaction mixtures were detected by standard tests¹⁰. Further, sulphate was estimated by gravimetric method¹¹. Benzenesulphonamide (BSA), the reduced product of the oxidant was detected by tlc employing ether-chloroform-n-butanol (2:2:1, v/v) as solvent and iodine as detecting reagent (R_f=0.88). The observed stoichiometry may be represented by equation (1),

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation were investigated at several [DCB]₀, [NCS⁻]₀ and [HClO₄] in 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol medium. The plots of log ([DCB]₀/[DCB]) vs time were linear upto at least 75% completion of the reaction and the pseudo-first order rate constants were unaffected by the changes in [DCB]₀ (Table 1), showing first order

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (*k*_{obs}) FOR OXIDATION OF THIOCYANATE ION BY DICHLORAMINE-B (DCB) IN 50% (v/v) AQUEOUS METHANOL MEDIUM AT 273 K

[DCB] ₀ × 10 ³	[X] (mol dm ⁻³) [NCS ⁻] ₀ × 10 ³	[HClO ₄] × 10 ³	[H ⁺] × 10 ³	<i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	μ* mol dm ⁻³	<i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
0.3	2.0	5.0	4.56	4.4	0.07	4.9
0.5	2.0	5.0	4.56	4.5	0.1	4.7
1.0	2.0	5.0	4.56	4.6	0.3	4.6
2.0	2.0	5.0	4.56	4.6	0.5	4.4
1.0	1.0	5.0	4.56	3.2	% Methanol ^a	
1.0	2.0	5.0	4.56	4.6	10	4.9
1.0	4.0	5.0	4.56	6.5	40	4.7
1.0	10.0	5.0	4.56	9.5	50	4.6
1.0	20.0	5.0	4.56	12.6	70	4.3
1.0	2.0	1.0	0.96	3.3	80	4.2
1.0	2.0	2.0	1.88	3.8	[BSA] ^a	
1.0	2.0	5.0	4.56	4.6	(× 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³)	
1.0	2.0	10.0	8.77	5.4	0.0	4.6
1.0	2.0	20.0	16.54	6.4	0.5	4.6
1.0	2.0	5.0	4.56	4.6 [†]	1.0	4.9
1.0	2.0	5.0	4.56	4.7 [‡]	2.0	5.2
1.0	2.0	5.0	4.56	4.9 [‡]	4.0	5.6
1.0	2.0	5.0	4.56	5.1 [‡]	—	—

(1) 0.0 (2) 0.5 (3) 1.0 (4) 2.0 for [KCl] (× 10³ mol dm⁻³).

*[DCB]₀ = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [NCS⁻]₀ = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ and 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol medium.

^aSame as (*) except for the medium and μ = 0.3 mol dm⁻³.

kinetics in $[\text{DCB}]_0$. At constant $[\text{DCB}]_0$ and $[\text{HClO}_4]$, the rate increased with increase in $[\text{NCS}^-]$. The $[\text{NCS}^-]$ was varied at three different temperatures. The plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [\text{NCS}^-]$ were linear with fractional slopes (~ 0.5) indicating fractional order dependence of rate on $[\text{NCS}^-]$. The effect of $[\text{H}^+]$ on the rate of oxidation was investigated by adding varying amounts of perchloric acid ($0.01-0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) (Table 1). The rate increased with the increase in $[\text{H}^+]$ and the plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [\text{H}^+]$ was linear with a fractional slope of 0.25 showing fractional order kinetics in $[\text{H}^+]$.

Addition of the reaction product, benzenesulphonamide (BSA) and Cl^- had negligible effects on the rate. Decrease in dielectric constant of the medium by changing the solvent composition from 10/50% to 80/20% (Table 1) decreased the rate. The rates were measured at different temperatures and the activation parameters computed as described under discussion.

The observed kinetics of first order in $[\text{DCB}]$, fractional order each in $[\text{NCS}^-]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ can be accounted by Michaelis-Menten type mechanism (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1 leads to the rate law (2),

$$-\frac{d[\text{DCB}]}{dt} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{DCB}]_0 [\text{NCS}^-] [\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_1 K_2 [\text{NCS}^-] [\text{H}^+]}$$

or

$$k_{obs} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{NCS}^-] [\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_1 K_2 [\text{NCS}^-] [\text{H}^+]} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1}{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{NCS}^-] [\text{H}^+]} + \frac{1}{k_3} \quad (3)$$

The $[\text{NCS}^-]$ was varied at three different temperatures and the plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{NCS}^-]$ were linear with finite intercepts at all temperatures (Fig. 1), in conformity with the rate law (3). The disproportionation constant (k_3) of the complex was calculated at different temperatures from the intercepts of the plots, k_3 ($\times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) values are 1.1, 1.8 and 2.5 respectively, at 273, 278 and 283 K. The plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ was also linear (Fig. 1). The activation parameters have been

calculated from the Arrhenius plots of $\log k_3$ vs $1/T$ and $\log (k_3/T)$ vs $1/T$. The values are 7.1, 54.4 kJ mol^{-1} , 52.1 kJ mol^{-1} , $-26.0 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and 59.2 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively, for $\log A$, E_a , ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger .

Fig. 1. (A) Plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$; $[\text{DCB}]_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 273 K, $\mu = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol. (B) Plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$; $[\text{DCB}]_0 = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{NCS}^-]_0 = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 273 K; $\mu = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol.

The proposed mechanism is also in conformity with the observed negligible influence of ionic strength of the medium and the reaction products, BSA and Cl^- . The detailed mechanism of oxidation is shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

The thiocyanic or isothiocyanic acid reacts with dichloramine-B (RNCl_2) giving CINCS or NCSCl . The NCSCl further reacts with RNHCl and RNCl_2 and undergoes hydrolysis in fast steps^{5,6} to give sulphate and cyanates as final products. The decrease of rate with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium is also in conformity with Amis¹² and other concepts¹³.

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Flow Behaviour of Bentonite Suspension. Part-II. Interaction with Inorganic and Organic Polyions

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THE protective and sensitising effect of hydrophilic colloids on hydrophobic sol has been known for long time but the detailed study with respect to interaction of polyelectrolytes with clay suspension is yet to be undertaken. This provides one of the ways of probing the mechanism involved in such process. Kajisaki *et al.*¹ studied the effect of K-polyacrylate as a deflocculant which increased

the plasticity to some degree. Joyce and Worrall² studied the adsorption of polyphosphate on two kaolinitic clays and found that adsorption is mainly physical rather than anion-exchange in nature. Bentonite clay is more sensitive towards aqueous phase interaction in comparison to other clays and is one of the best varieties available in India.

Experimental

Bihar bentonite clay, collected in lump form, was purified³ from the associated impurities like quartz, feldspar, calcite, organic matters and water soluble alkali salts and a definite size fraction (1 μ and below) was collected. Purified Bihar bentonite was converted into Na-form and its characteristics are as follows: constituents (% w/w) SiO₂, 51.30; Al₂O₃, 21.31; Fe₂O₃, 1.41; MgO, 1.36; loss on ignition, 14.89; cation exchange capacity (meq/100 g) 97.20; DTA peak temp. (°C), 155, 565 (endo), 940 (exo).

Solution of each of the polyelectrolytes, like Na-silicate, Na-hexametaphosphate, Na-polyacrylate, Na-amylose phosphate, Na-lauryl sulphate, polyvinyl alcohol, gelatin and Na-carboxymethylcellulose, was added in increasing amounts to 10% Na-bentonite suspension for study of its rheological behaviour. The plastic viscosity and yield value were determined in a modified McMichael viscometer utilising Reiner and Rewlin equation⁴ for plastic flow in a rotational viscometer as a function of addition of polyelectrolytes.

Results and Discussion

The interaction of the macromolecular compounds with bentonite is quite different from that of electrolytes as studied and reported in a previous communication⁵. The yield value and plastic viscosity values are given in Table I.

Plastic viscosity was found to increase on addition of polyelectrolytes as compared to the original value without any addition. Inorganic polyions, Na-carboxymethyl cellulose and Na-polyacrylate showed continuous increase of plastic viscosity. Viscosity is very much dependent on solvent-solute interaction. Na-carboxymethylcellulose is very much susceptible to polymerisation and a very good complexing agent for Al³⁺ which resides at the edge of the clay crystal and is responsible for the positive charge. Amongst the inorganic dispersing agents, sodium silicate is a more effective polymerising material. The viscosity was minimum with Na-lauryl sulphate although Na-lauryl sulphate and polyvinyl alcohol behave in the same fashion—the viscosity initially increased, reached a maximum and sharply decreased. Rapid decrease of viscosity might be due to the decrease in solvent-solute interaction resulting in coagulation of the system. But in the case of amylose phosphate and gelatin, the viscosity increased on